

USAGE OF DIFFERENT METHODS AND TECHNIQUES IN COMMUNICATIVE LANGUAGE TEACHING

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Abstract:

This article describes importance of speaking in teaching. Learning a language through communication is one of the most effective ways. Initially, this process seems difficult and impossible however after a few exercises, and attempts, the outcome will be amazing. In the process of learning this skill, it is important to learn more vocabulary, and more complex grammar rules. Effective teaching of communication in a foreign language can fundamentally change the quality of intermediate education.

Key words: communicative, ESL, Role-playing, poems, riddles, childhood, conversation, speech.

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Nowadays learning to communicate in the target language is useful. From the beginner level, every learner needs ways to increase interest in communication. Therefore, it is significant to transfer speaking skills in a more inductive teaching way. CLT activities are most effective when students are allowed to work together in pairs or groups. Research has shown ESL pupils generally feel more confident and comfortable applying their language skills and ideas when working with other students. Because they work with English Language Learners, they feel more secure in communicating without fear of making mistakes.

The most common educational model used in the context of the communicative method is the functional-notional approach, which emphasizes the organization of the curriculum. For example, we can consider the following methodological processes in teaching communicative language:

- The role of scenes and interactive conversation in the development of oral speech.
- The role of conversation and oral speech in the effective organization of the lesson process
- Cooperation within the group (student and teacher cooperation).
- Collaborate within the group to improve information exchange.
- an important factor in expressing personal opinion during group work

The monitoring ability of the teacher should be very group work, the teacher focuses on fluency but not exactly. During pair and group work, the teacher focuses on accuracy by correcting mistakes, because students need to understand their own mistakes.

The CLT approach is great for intermediate and advanced learners, but

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beginners need some supervised practice. Adopting a communicative approach raises important issues; teacher training, materials development, testing. So it is not suitable for every teacher and every class.

Example:

1. The teacher sets the scene: where is the conversation going.
2. The teacher determines the purpose of the students' conversation. (For example, the speaker is asking for directions, the speaker is ordering coffee, the speaker is talking about a movie he just saw, etc.)
3. The students converse in pairs for a designated amount of time.

Role-playing is a useful communication technique when participants require a confidence boost. This is because using role play is a surefire way to encourage participants to look beyond their worries and fears. Role-playing as someone other than themselves also allows participants to recognize that their anxieties are often unfounded or exaggerated. This activity gives students an opportunity to improve their target language communication skills in a low-pressure situation. Most students are more comfortable speaking in pairs rather than in front of the whole class.

The teacher should know the difference between conversation and speech. Students may use the same words over and over in this activity and not actually have a creative conversation. If teachers do not regulate how students have conversations, then students may not truly develop their communication skills. Role-playing allows employees to rehearse difficult situations before they actually occur. This often allows them to see that the situation is more positive than they thought. For a group of 4–8 students, using a single role play with a faculty mentor asking the group for input and feedback can be very successful, as most or all of the students can take an active role at some point. They pressured them to speak if they had little to say. The simplest version of this is a visual role-playing game. This is an observed role play in which the teacher and the "patient" participate in a communication encounter that can then be deconstructed with a small group. Students can be given specific roles to observe, such as attending to non-verbal cues, the patient's emotions. This tact can allow for discussion of the cognitive approach and identification of affect. Role-playing is a method that businesses often use to build trust among employees. Since colleagues work regularly with each other, effective employee collaboration is integral to the company's well-being. Using role-playing in the workplace can be a simple process, and businesses can benefit from the ability to do it in a variety of ways. Individuals initiate the role-playing process by identifying the scenario the participants are to act out. This scenario can be fictional or based on a situation that has happened or will happen in real life. After defining the scenario, gather the participants to discuss the scene they want to role-play. Role-playing is usually more successful when the participants fully agree to participate.

A third person in the triad may provide feedback to the clinician, which students participate in, but often results in feedback that is less specific and less effective than that provided by the teacher. This approach is appropriate when communication skills are not particularly difficult and the teacher wants all members to have the opportunity to practice discrete skills. A more advanced version is a whole-group "hot seat" role-play where one student talks to a "patient" in front of a small group, assisted by a teacher. This approach creates the most anxiety among students, but if done skillfully, can lead to lively learning. This allows one or two students to develop deep skills and develops observational skills in the rest of the group. This approach requires the teacher to have sophisticated skills in student management and role-play management. In the demonstration role-play, students can identify areas in which they want to strengthen their observational skills, such as non-

verbal communication. The learner can then focus on an aspect of communication skills that allows for deeper learning.

One of the most effective methods is the interview method. This method can encourage the students speaking ability. An interview is an oral activity carried out in pairs, the main purpose of which is to develop students' interaction in target language. Thus, an interview is a communication process that uses questions and answers. It is effective in learning speaking because it can stimulate the brain to think. During the interview, the interviewer opens the question and the interviewer listens and answers the question. According to the results research, a form of interview method students are asked for certain interviews people, including classmates.

At first interviews are usually held during the semester class where only students are asked interviewing their classmates. Someone's verbal through interview technique language skills are taught due to interaction between one person and another. A one student said something similar emphasized that through the interview technique, one would be trained to provide and answer other people's questions directly. Also, interview techniques can be taught someone to think quickly and practically because we have to answer or try to answer at that time someone asks a question a question.

Another point about the interview technique, through this technique, students not only ask or answer questions interview questions and learn more additional skills such as asking questions and answer others' questions politely, how to choose good questions and how to think fast and accurate. Interview technique also helps to broaden horizons and communicate with others because you should do the interaction of two or more people interview process. They say that through this technique, a person speech skills increase. This technique is also believed increase students' confidence in speaking. An interview is a conversation a process that uses questions and answers answer effective conversation is used to study speech because it can stimulate brain to think. During the conversation, interviewers reveal questions and interviewers listen and then answer the questions. Each one they then receive a message to compare it with the knowledge they have. It can be done communication is more dynamic and meaningful. An interview is a conversation a process that uses questions and answers answer Effective conversation is used study speech because it can be motivating brain to think. During the interview, reveal questions and interviewers listen and then answer the questions. Each one then they get a message to compare with the knowledge they have. It can be done communication is more dynamic and meaningful.

So we need the situation and the topic to give students the cognitive space to focus

On the skill they are using rather than the language. We need to make sure it is familiar. They must place in interaction. For example, maintaining fluency while trying to hold the floor is best applied in a subject area where the student is comfortable. A simple way to do this is to set the practice on a topic that the students are familiar with and have difficulty talking about with each other.

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